

Supporting tables_Prajakta Patil et al

Table 1: Parameter analyzed during the BMP experiment

	Parameters	Method/Instrument used
1.	Biogas	Water displacement unit
2.	pH	Oakton pH meter
3.	Total Solids (TS)	APHA 2015
4.	Volatile Solids (VS)	APHA 2015
5.	Volatile Fatty Acids (VFA)	APHA 1998
6.	Biogas composition (CH ₄ , CO ₂ , H ₂ S)	Gas Chromatography (Trace 1110_ThermoFisher Scientific)
7.	<i>A. suum</i> Inactivation	Pebsworth et al. 2012

Table 2: Variations in parameters during EC experiment (Generated hypochlorite)

Ratio	0hr	15 min	30 min	1h	2h	3h	4h	5h	6h	24h
1:30 (156 ppm)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
1:20 (235 ppm)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
1:10 (470 ppm)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
1:5 (940 ppm)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	7.2
No dilution (4700ppm)	8	7	7	6	5	5	4	3	3	2